

Selection of Photovoltaic Solar Power Plant Investment Projects - An ANP Approach

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Abstract—In this paper the Analytic Network Process (ANP) is applied to the selection of photovoltaic (PV) solar power projects. These projects follow a long management and execution process from plant site selection to plant start-up. As a consequence, there are many risks of time delays and even of project stoppage.

In the case study presented in this paper a top manager of an important Spanish company that operates in the power market has to decide on the best PV project (from four alternative projects) to invest based on risk minimization. The manager identified 50 project execution delay and/or stoppage risks.

The influences among elements of the network (groups of risks and alternatives) were identified and analyzed using the ANP multicriteria decision analysis method. After analyzing the results the main conclusion is that the network model can manage all the information of the real-world problem and thus it is a decision analysis model recommended by the authors. The strengths and weaknesses ANP as a multicriteria decision analysis tool are also described in the paper.

Keywords—Multicriteria decision analysis, Analytic Network Process, Photovoltaic solar power projects.

I. INTRODUCTION

INVESTMENT projects in photovoltaic solar power plants are becoming more and more promising and popular in Spain. Spain has very good conditions for the development of solar power systems due mainly to the high mean daily radiation (amount of mean daily radiation per land surface unit) and the high number of sunny days in most parts of the country. For this reason, the Administration and companies working in the sector are developing policies and investing in photovoltaic solar power systems. A photovoltaic solar plant, also known as a solar power farm, consists of a number of photovoltaic solar panels placed in a specific site with the purpose of selling the generated energy to the contracting electricity supply company. The amount of energy generated ranges between 3 MWp (Megawatt peak) and 50 MWp

Conventional power plants like nuclear or combined-cycle power plants require important investments only affordable to

big power supply companies. By contrast, the investment required in the development of solar power plants is considerably lower and thus affordable to smaller companies or individual investors. For this reason, many companies smaller than the big electricity supply companies are starting to position in this market and are investing in solar power.

The present paper analyzes the problem for the managing board of an important solar power investment company to establish a priority order among different projects for the development of a photovoltaic solar power plant. The company of this case study is a medium-sized company traditionally devoted to the installation and maintenance of power systems for the big power supply companies, but which has recently entered the market of power generation through the development, maintenance and exploitation of solar power plants.

The decision problem presented here is highly complex because in addition to economic profitability, the risks involved in the development, construction, execution and maintenance of the plant are relevant factors in the decision making process. Therefore the priority value assigned to each project depends on the economic profitability and execution time of the projects. Investment companies that execute the project and further exploit the installations cannot have their resources inactive while waiting for the corresponding construction approval and execution permits, which may get delayed, or depend on long negotiations with the power supply company.

A solar power plant project, from the very first stage of selection of the plant site and land survey, to the last stage of implementation and start-up of the plant, follows a long process that involves obtaining the required construction permits and authorizations (Table I), negotiating with the different stakeholders (land owners, local and government authorities, power supply companies), complying with complex legal regulations, as well as solving the technical problems related to the construction of the plant and the distribution of the energy generated. This management process for the obtaining of the required construction and execution permits and development of the plant makes projects that can be very profitable at the exploitation stage be also very risky due to unexpected project execution delays or even project stoppage.

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TABLE I
DIAGRAM OF THE REQUIRED CONSTRUCTION AND EXECUTION PERMITS AND LICENSES

	PRELIMINARY ISSUES	FINAL ISSUES
Local administration	Construction license	Business Activity License
Electric grid manager	Electric grid connection point	Final connection to the grid. Contract
Competent Body Autonomous Regions	Administrative approval. Provisional registration in the Register of Production Facilities in special Regime	Certificate of plant Start-up. LV certificate Registration in the Register of Production Facilities in special Regime
Public Tax Administration	Registration in EAT (Economic Activity Tax)	Business Activity Code

This paper presents a decision-making method based on the Analytic Network Process (ANP) [1], [2] that may help the managing board of a company of this kind to solve the following decision-making problem: "Given a number of photovoltaic power investment projects that are known to be profitable for the company, establish project priority based on project risk levels and execution time delays."

The procedure proposed here allows identifying, weighting and estimating the risks involved in the development of solar power projects, and establishing priorities based on this risk analysis. For that, a network-based ANP model has been used in the study. The resulting data and the overall process have been analyzed on the basis of the time devoted by the decision maker and his degree of satisfaction with the analysis procedure and the final results.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Firstly, Section II introduces the Analytic Network Process. Then, Section III describes the decision making process and Section IV presents the main conclusions derived from this research and future works.

II. BACKGROUND OF ANP

ANP represents a decision making problem as a network of criteria and alternatives (all called elements), grouped into clusters. All the elements in the network can be related in any possible way, i.e. a network can incorporate feedback and interdependence relationships within and between clusters. This provides a more accurate modelling of complex settings. The influence of the elements in the network on other elements in that network can be represented in a supermatrix. This new concept consists of a two-dimensional element-by-element matrix which adjusts the relative importance weights in individual pairwise comparison matrices to build a new overall supermatrix with the eigenvectors of the adjusted relative importance weights. According to Saaty [2], the ANP model comprises the following steps:

- (i) Identifying the components and elements of the network and their relationships.
- (ii) Conducting pairwise comparisons on the elements.
- (iii) Placing the resulting relative importance weights (eigenvectors) in pairwise comparison matrices within the supermatrix (unweighted supermatrix).
- (iv) Conducting pairwise comparisons on the clusters.
- (v) Weighting the blocks of the unweighted supermatrix,

by the corresponding priorities of the clusters, so that it can be column stochastic (weighted supermatrix).

(vi) Raising the weighted supermatrix to limiting powers until the weights converge and remain stable (limit supermatrix).

More details on the Analytic Network Process (ANP) can be found in [1], however, the main steps are summarized here for completeness.

Some of the most recent applications of ANP to decision making problems have been: R&D project selection [3], [4], construction project selection [5]; resource allocation in transportation [6]; enterprise information system project selection with regard to BOCR [7]; supplier selection [8], selection of logistics service provider [9], contractor selection [10], purchasing decisions [11]; solid waste disposal options [12], locating undesirable facilities [13]; concept evaluation in a new product development [14]; evaluation of alternative fuels for residential heating [15], strategic e-business decision analysis [16], asset valuation [17], [18], choice of best management alternative of the supply chain in a company [19], determination of the appropriate energy policy [20], product mix planning [21], selection of best actuation for end-of-life computers [22].

The reasons for using an ANP-based decision analysis approach in the present work are: (i) Risk-based project selection is a multicriteria decision problem, (ii) there are dependences among groups of risks and between these and the projects under evaluation that have to be analyzed, (iii) the detailed analysis of interdependences between clusters forces the decision maker to carefully reflect on his/her project priority approach and on the decision-making problem itself, which results in a better knowledge of the problem and a more reliable final decision.

III. THE DECISION MAKING PROCESS AND THE ANP MODELING APPROACH

A. Description of the Decision Making Process

The decision-making process followed in the study was divided into three phases: problem analysis, synthesis and evaluation. The study was developed jointly by the research team of the Department of Engineering Projects of the Polytechnic University of Valencia, who are experts in MCDA and played the role of Analysis Team (EA), and a top manager of the investment company who is an expert in the management and execution of photovoltaic solar power plant projects and who played the role of Decision Maker (DM). Fig. 1 shows the decision-making process followed in the study.

Fig. 1 Decision making process

B. Phase of Problem Analysis

In this phase the problem was defined. At the first two meetings between the Analysis Team and the Decision Maker the decision problem was formulated and the main goal of the analysis process was identified as mentioned in the Introduction of the paper. Next, the stages involved in the development of a photovoltaic solar power plant were analyzed and the possible risks associated with each stage of the project were identified. From the project portfolio of the company, the decision maker selected four alternatives. Following is a description of the different stages of the process.

C. Analysis of the Stages of a Photovoltaic Solar Power Plant Project

At this stage the process of developing a photovoltaic solar power plant was analyzed from the selection of the best plant site to the execution, exploitation and maintenance of the plant. Annex 1 shows a list of the different steps of the process. This analysis allowed the DM to identify project delay or stoppage risks for each stage of the process.

D. Risk Identification

For the identification of risks, in addition to the project analysis mentioned above, social, legal, political, as well as technical and economic factors were taken into consideration. These factors are mutually related. Since this step is essential in the decision-making process, risk identification was done in an iterative way. In the first iteration the DM elaborated a list of risks grouped by concepts associated with the different steps of the project. The risks in turn were grouped into six specific categories: political risks (P), technical risks (T), economic risks (E), time delay risks (T), legal risks (L) and social risks (S). In the second iteration, the risks were put into these categories, and some risks which could fall into two

categories were re-defined so as to obtain a final well-defined classification of risks. Finally 50 bottom-level risks were identified grouped into 16 second-level sub-groups. The 16 sub-groups in turn were grouped into 6 high-level groups or categories. Table II shows the different risk categories grouped as mentioned above.

TABLE II
RISK IDENTIFICATION AND CLASSIFICATION
GOAL: Risk Maximization

Political Risks	
Macroeconomic	
C1	Changes in the Energy Policy
Urban planning	
C2	Obtaining of the Local Body approval
C3	Obtaining of Construction License
Technical Risks	
Associated with the plant location	
C4	Technological adequacy to climate change
C5	Estimation of flood risks
C6	Estimation of effective solar radiation hours
C7	Earthworks
C8	Geotechnical problems of the terrain
Associated with technology	
C9	Development of new photovoltaic solar power systems
C10	Selection of the PV cell
C11	Selection of inverter
C12	Selection of solar tracker
C13	Connection to the electric grid
C14	Possibility of alternative power generation systems
Economic Risks	
Associated with plant exploitation	
C15	Plant operation costs
C16	Corrective maintenance costs
C17	Prevention maintenance costs
C18	Performance losses
Associated with plant location	
C19	Revenue estimation based on effective solar radiation time
C20	Revenue estimation due to the climate change
C21	Earthworks Resources
C22	Flood prevention works
C23	Solution of geotechnical problems
Associated with plant start-up permits	
C24	Costs of connection to electric grid
C25	Costs of agreement with land owner
C26	Possibility of constructing the power connection line
C27	Economic risks related to the obtaining of the construction license
Associated with technology	
C28	Costs due to wrong selection of PV cell
C29	Costs due to wrong selection of inverter
C30	Costs due to lack of consistency in the selection of the solar tracker
Macroeconomic	
C31	Obtaining of bank financing
C32	Changes in power demand
C33	Changes in the price of money

C34	Changes in energy prices
Time Delay Risks	
Connection to Electric grid	
C35	Delays in the construction of the power connection line
C36	Delays in the obtaining of the administration approval for the construction of the line
C37	Delays in the obtaining of plant Start-up Act
C38	Delays in the signature of the agreement with the Electricity supply company
Urban planning	
C39	Delays in the obtaining of the Local Body Approval
C40	Delays in the obtaining of the EIS
C41	Delays in the obtaining of the construction license
Legal Risks	
Associated with legal issues	
C42	Changes in specific legislation
C43	Changes in general legislation
Connection to Electric grid	
C44	Legislative changes in the Administrative Authorization of the power distribution line
C45	Legislative changes in the obtaining of the plant Start-up Act
C46	Obtaining of the Registration in the Register of Production Facilities in special Regime
Urban planning	
C47	Legislative changes in the EIS
Social Risks	
Related to Plant Exploitation	
C48	Thefts
C49	Vandalism
Urban planning	
C50	Social consequences resulting from land acquisition

recommended by the ANP method. This was solved by defining additional economic and technical clusters with less than 9 elements each. In this way, the resulting network contains 12 clusters (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 ANP network model

E. Specification of the Company's Project Portfolio

At this stage, the DM identified the projects that were used as alternatives in the decision process. Project selection was based on criteria of economic profitability, and technical and environmental feasibility. Four projects with different characteristics and plant location were finally selected. Annex 2 shows the main features of the four selected projects.

F. Phase of Data Synthesis

In this phase, the ANP procedure was used: the risks were weighted; then each alternative was valued for each risk so as to obtain the desired final priority order of the projects under study.

• The ANP Model

This model consists of elements grouped into clusters. The elements of a cluster can be related to elements of another cluster or to elements of the same cluster (feedback). The alternatives form an additional cluster.

• Determination of the Network

The first step of the ANP method is the representation of the decision problem using a network model. This requires a deep knowledge of the problem by the DM and the advice given by the AT based on the data collected in previous stages. The steps needed for the construction of the network are: i) determination of the elements, ii) determination of the clusters, and iii) determination of the influence network. The first step has been described above in the section Problem Analysis. In order to establish the clusters, six risk categories were identified (political, technical, economic, time delays, legal and social); however, the economic and technical clusters contained more than 9 elements, which is not

For the determination of the influences a zero-one interfactorial dominance matrix was used [2] whose elements a_{ij} take the value 1 or 0 depending on whether there is or there is not some influence of element i on element j . The rows and columns of the matrix are formed by all the elements of the network.

In ANP, this numerical data can be represented graphically and thus show the influence pattern of the network. This step is essential for the further development of the process because if all the complexity of the real-world case study is to be transferred to the model, the DM has to accurately identify the influences of some elements upon others based on his knowledge and experience. If the DM fails to identify one influence, the model will not take it into account and some valuable information will be lost. For this reason the DM was asked about the influences that each risk exerted on the other risks and on the alternatives and vice versa. As there are 50 risks in the model, this means 2500 questions of the type "Do you think that risk R_i has any influence on R_j ?". To facilitate the DM's task, the AT designed a questionnaire, organized into clusters and divided into two steps. In the first step the DM was asked to analyze the criteria groups, e.g. the "political criteria", and to reflect on "whether any element of the group influences or is influenced by any of the risks belonging to another group, e.g. the "technical risks". The actual wording of the question is "In your opinion, does any political risk have influence on any technical risk?" The DM then only had to tick the Yes or No box in the questionnaire.

In the second step another questionnaire was designed in which the DM was asked about element-to-element relationships, but only for those clusters in which the DM had marked the existence of some relationship in the previous questionnaire. In this way many detail questions were eliminated from the questionnaire, which facilitated the DM's task. Thus the 2500 possible questions were simplified to 969 (the group of alternatives was supposed to influence and be

influenced by all the risks). The questionnaire was organized into groups in such a way that the questions about external influences, i.e. possible influences among risks belonging to different clusters, were asked first, and then the questions about internal influences, i.e., feedback or influences among risks within the same cluster. Annex 3 shows the resulting interfactorial dominance matrix.

With the data obtained from the questionnaire the decision model was built with the help of the Super Decisions v1.6.0. software (www.superdecisions.com). Fig. 3 shows the relationships among the clusters.

Fig. 3 Structure of the relationship among the clusters of the ANP network

• *Determination of Element and Cluster Priorities*

This stage includes all the steps of the ANP model. The first step consists of assigning priorities to related elements in order to build the unweighted supermatrix. For this end, each risk is analyzed in terms of which other risks have influence upon it; then the corresponding pairwise comparison matrices of each risk group are generated in order to obtain the corresponding eigenvectors.

The procedure is the following: let's suppose that some or all the elements (risks) e_{ik} of cluster C_k influence one element e_{ij} of cluster C_j (e.g. the three risks of the cluster "economic risks associated with technology" have influence on the risk "prevention maintenance costs" of the cluster "economic risks associated with exploitation"). To determine which elements (among those that have some kind of influence) of C_k have more influence on element e_{ij} of C_j , a reciprocal pairwise comparison matrix is built with the elements of C_k . In order to fill in each component of the matrix $n(n-1)/2$ questions (n being the number of risks of C_k that influence e_{ij}) have to be answered. This procedure is repeated for each cluster whose elements exert some influence on element e_{ij} of C_j . In this way, for each column of the e_{ij} elements of the unweighted supermatrix we can identify blocks corresponding to each of the clusters that exert some kind of influence on that element and whose values form the eigenvector that represents the

relative influence of the elements of each cluster on element e_{ij} .

As in the case study different risks from different clusters have influences on one risk cluster the unweighted matrix is non-stochastic by columns. Thus, according to [2], all clusters that exert any kind of influence upon each group have to be prioritized using the corresponding cluster pairwise comparison matrices. The value corresponding to the priority associated with a certain cluster weights the priorities of the elements of the cluster on which it acts (in the unweighted supermatrix), and thus the weighted supermatrix can be generated. Annex 3 shows the unweighted and weighted matrices

For this end, a new questionnaire about priorities was designed to be answered by the DM. This questionnaire analyzed each risk in terms of which of the other risks that have influence on it and belong to a certain cluster exerts a greater influence on it and to what extent. This is done by means of the pairwise comparison. The DM had to answer 332 questions in this model. Additionally the questionnaire had questions specifically designed to determine the priorities among clusters. This meant 200 additional questions. The questionnaire was designed as a multiple-choice test into tables that grouped the questions relative to the pairwise comparison matrices. Tables III and IV show an example of the questionnaire.

With respect to the criterion "achievement in the obtaining of the construction license", which criterion from the following criteria belonging to the group "time delays" exerts the greatest influence and to what extent?

TABLE III
 EXAMPLE OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE ABOUT PRIORITIZATION OF ELEMENTS

Criterion with the greatest influence			To what extent?
Delays in the Local Body Approval	☒	Delays in the obtaining of the EIS	☐ "In this box the DM writes a value of the 1-9 scale"
Delays in the Local Body Approval	☒	Delays in the obtaining of the construction license	☐
Delays in the obtaining of the EIS	☒	Delays in the obtaining of the construction license	☐

With respect to the cluster of "Technical" risks associated with "features of the plant site", which cluster exerts the strongest influence and to what extent?

TABLE IV

EXAMPLE OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE ABOUT PRIORITIZATION OF CLUSTERS

Cluster with the greatest influence			To what extent?
Alternatives	☐	Legal criteria	☐
Alternatives	☐	Technical criteria associated with features of the plant site	☐
Alternatives	☐	Technical criteria associated with technology	☐
Legal criteria	☐	Technical criteria associated with features of the plant site	☐
Legal criteria	☐	Technical criteria associated with technology	☐
Technical criteria associated with features of the plant site	☐	Technical criteria associated with technology	☐

- Calculation of the limit matrix and resulting prioritization.

By raising the weighted supermatrix to successive powers the limit matrix is obtained. The results of the model are shown in Tables V and VI and in Annex 4.

G. Phase of Evaluation of Results

Table V shows the results obtained in the study. The “best” alternative is the alternative with the overall “lower risk” and therefore the alternative with the “lowest” value. The alternative selected as the best option is alternative A3, which is the alternative with the lowest risks throughout the execution process, from project formulation to plant start-up. The priority order shown is A3 P A4 P A1 P A2, alternative A2 being by far the alternative with the highest risks.

TABLE V

PRIORITIES OF SOLAR PLANT PROJECTS IN % ACCORDING TO THE ANP MODEL

A1	28.32
A2	40.95
A3	14.64
A4	16.07

Table VI shows the comparison of the 15 risks with the highest importance or influence in each model. The cluster to which the risk belongs is shown in brackets: P = political risk, E = economic risk, T = time delay risk, S = social risk, L = legal risk, I = technical risk. Annex 4 shows the weights of all risks calculated with each model.

TABLE VI

PRIORITIES OF THE 15 RISKS WITH THE HIGHEST IMPORTANCE/INFLUENCE (IN %)

risks	Weight (%)
C1 (P)	12.04
C50 (S)	10.74
C40 (T)	6.53
C48 (S)	6.48
C47 (L)	6.44
C2 (P)	6.07
C19 (E)	4.59
C39 (T)	4.19
C30 (E)	2.87
C22 (E)	2.69
C43 (L)	2.55
C38 (T)	2.36
C49 (S)	2.14
C18 (E)	2.05
C42 (L)	1.56

The two most relevant risks are “changes in the energy policy” (C1) and “social consequences resulting from land acquisition” (it evaluates the risk that some social sector stands against the project) (C50).

With these results the question issued by the DM was: if only the alternative projects are analyzed, it is clear that projects A3 and A4 are the best alternatives provided there is enough money to develop two projects. The ANP model supports this decision.

The DM agreed to use the results obtained with the Network ANP model, despite the fact that then risk analysis depends on the particular alternative under analysis. As stated by Saaty (2001, op.cit. 96) “the entries of the weighted supermatrix itself give the direct influence of any element on any other. But an element can influence a second element indirectly through its influence on some third element and then by the influence of that element on the second”. There can be many hidden influences through indirect relationships. Therefore, because we wish to capture the transmission of influence along all possible paths of the supermatrix, we need to raise the supermatrix to powers. The ANP model takes into consideration all the influences perceived by the DM. However, the authors want to reflect upon the complexity of the model. This is the main weakness and also the main strength of the method: weakness in the sense of the complexity of the model, and strength in the sense of the reflections, experience and deep knowledge gained by the DM on the case study.

Further analysis will allow discussion on whether certain risks can be neglected or should be included in the analysis of

the alternatives. Thus, in further similar decision making problems with other alternative projects under study, the information about risk influences provided by the DM can be used in the new decision process and only the mutual influences between risks and alternatives will have to be studied.

It is worth mentioning that, since the DM possessed a deep knowledge on this kind of projects, the results coincided with his initial intuition. Despite the great efforts spent in answering the questionnaires, his conclusion was that he answered the questions fast and that the questions helped him reflect on the problem. This greatly helped him to select the best projects and to identify the risks with the greatest influences.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a practical application of the ANP method to the field of project selection. In the case study the investment company is particularly sensitive to these decisions since in addition to investing in the exploitation of photovoltaic solar power it also designs and builds the plants. Therefore delays in the execution of the project are considered very relevant as the company's resources cannot be inactive.

The novelty of the present approach is to consider the decision making process from the point of view of project risks and to take into consideration risk influences using ANP. ANP provides the relative importance of each criterion in terms of its influence on the other selection criteria and between criteria and alternatives. Results show that ANP generates evaluation results very close to the expert's intuition.

However, the use of ANP involves a number of considerations:

- The questionnaires to be answered by the DM have to be carefully designed (to allow for the correct analysis of influences among criteria and criteria prioritization).
- Cluster structure and components have to be well-defined to simplify the network as much as possible.
- Large models should be simplified either through subnets, semi-complete pairwise comparison matrices or less detailed models.

APPENDIX 1 STAGES OF A PHOTOVOLTAIC SOLAR POWER PLANT PROJECT

APPENDIX 2 CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOLAR POWER PLANT PROJECTS (ALTERNATIVES)

Alternative 1	
Name	Hoya de los Vicentes
Location	Jumilla (Murcia)
Voltage	20 MW
Power system	Single axle tracker
Land classification	Non urbanizable
Electrical connection system	132 kV Line
Land owner	Local Council of Jumilla
Environmental impact	No problems
Current situation of the Project	At an advanced stage

Alternative 2	
Name	Campo de Santa Teresa
Location	Lorca (Murcia)
Voltage	30 MW
Power system	Single axle tracker
Land classification	Non urbanizable
Electrical connection system	132kV line
Land owner	Private land owner with lease agreement with the builder
Environmental impact	No problems
Current situation of the Project	Preliminary stages pending

Alternative 3	
Name	Universidad Politécnica de Valencia
Location	Valencia (Valencia)
Voltage	4 MW
Power system	Fix
Land classification	Urban
Electrical connection system	20 kV line
Land owner	Universidad Politécnica de Valencia
Environmental impact	No problems
Current situation of the Project	Under feasibility study

APPENDIX 3
 INTERFACTORIAL DOMINANCE MATRIX

ALTERNATIVAS	POLITICOS				RIESGOS TÉCNICOS												RIESGOS ECONÓMICOS												RIESGOS DE TIEMPO							RIESGOS LEGISLATIVOS							SOCIALES				ALTERNATIVAS																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																						
	P1	P2	P3	P4	Técnicos asociados a la naturaleza del empleo						Técnicos asociados a la tecnología						Económicos asociados a la obtención de premios de patentes						Económicos asociados a la naturaleza del emprendimiento						Económicos asociados a la tecnología						Económicos asociados a la explotación						Económicos macro-económicos							C09	C08	C07	C06	C05	C04	C03	C02	C01	A1	A2	A3	A4																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																									
					T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	T9	T10	T11	T12	T13	T14	T15	T16	T17	T18	T19	T20	T21	T22	T23	T24	T25	T26	T27	T28	T29	T30	T31	T32	T33	T34	T35	T36	T37	T38	T39	T40	T41	T42	T43														T44	T45	T46	T47	T48	T49	T50	T51	T52	T53	T54	T55	T56	T57	T58	T59	T60	T61	T62	T63	T64	T65	T66	T67	T68	T69	T70	T71	T72	T73	T74	T75	T76	T77	T78	T79	T80	T81	T82	T83	T84	T85	T86	T87	T88	T89	T90	T91	T92	T93	T94	T95	T96	T97	T98	T99	T100	T101	T102	T103	T104	T105	T106	T107	T108	T109	T110	T111	T112	T113	T114	T115	T116	T117	T118	T119	T120	T121	T122	T123	T124	T125	T126	T127	T128	T129	T130	T131	T132	T133	T134	T135	T136	T137	T138	T139	T140	T141	T142	T143	T144	T145	T146	T147	T148	T149	T150	T151	T152	T153	T154	T155	T156	T157	T158	T159	T160	T161	T162	T163	T164	T165	T166	T167	T168	T169	T170	T171	T172	T173	T174	T175	T176	T177	T178	T179	T180	T181	T182	T183	T184	T185	T186	T187	T188	T189	T190	T191	T192	T193	T194	T195	T196	T197	T198	T199	T200	T201	T202	T203	T204	T205	T206	T207	T208	T209	T210	T211	T212	T213	T214	T215	T216	T217	T218	T219	T220	T221	T222	T223	T224	T225	T226	T227	T228	T229	T230	T231	T232	T233	T234	T235	T236	T237	T238	T239	T240	T241	T242	T243	T244	T245	T246	T247	T248	T249	T250	T251	T252	T253	T254	T255	T256	T257	T258	T259	T260	T261	T262	T263	T264	T265	T266	T267	T268	T269	T270	T271	T272	T273	T274	T275	T276	T277	T278	T279	T280	T281	T282	T283	T284	T285	T286	T287	T288	T289	T290	T291	T292	T293	T294	T295	T296	T297	T298	T299	T300	T301	T302	T303	T304	T305	T306	T307	T308	T309	T310	T311	T312	T313	T314	T315	T316	T317	T318	T319	T320	T321	T322	T323	T324	T325	T326	T327	T328	T329	T330	T331	T332	T333	T334	T335	T336	T337	T338	T339	T340	T341	T342	T343	T344	T345	T346	T347	T348	T349	T350	T351	T352	T353	T354	T355	T356	T357	T358	T359	T360	T361	T362	T363	T364	T365	T366	T367	T368	T369	T370	T371	T372	T373	T374	T375	T376	T377	T378	T379	T380	T381	T382	T383	T384	T385	T386	T387	T388	T389	T390	T391	T392	T393	T394	T395	T396	T397	T398	T399	T400	T401	T402	T403	T404	T405	T406	T407	T408	T409	T410	T411	T412	T413	T414	T415	T416	T417	T418	T419	T420	T421	T422	T423	T424	T425	T426	T427	T428	T429	T430	T431	T432	T433	T434	T435	T436	T437	T438	T439	T440	T441	T442	T443	T444	T445	T446	T447	T448	T449	T450	T451	T452	T453	T454	T455	T456	T457	T458	T459	T460	T461	T462	T463	T464	T465	T466	T467	T468	T469	T470	T471	T472	T473	T474	T475	T476	T477	T478	T479	T480	T481	T482	T483	T484	T485	T486	T487	T488	T489	T490	T491	T492	T493	T494	T495	T496	T497	T498	T499	T500	T501	T502	T503	T504	T505	T506	T507	T508	T509	T510	T511	T512	T513	T514	T515	T516	T517	T518	T519	T520	T521	T522	T523	T524	T525	T526	T527	T528	T529	T530	T531	T532	T533	T534	T535	T536	T537	T538	T539	T540	T541	T542	T543	T544	T545	T546	T547	T548	T549	T550	T551	T552	T553	T554	T555	T556	T557	T558	T559	T560	T561	T562	T563	T564	T565	T566	T567	T568	T569	T570	T571	T572	T573	T574	T575	T576	T577	T578	T579	T580	T581	T582	T583	T584	T585	T586	T587	T588	T589	T590	T591	T592	T593	T594	T595	T596	T597	T598	T599	T600	T601	T602	T603	T604	T605	T606	T607	T608	T609	T610	T611	T612	T613	T614	T615	T616	T617	T618	T619	T620	T621	T622	T623	T624	T625	T626	T627	T628	T629	T630	T631	T632	T633	T634	T635	T636	T637	T638	T639	T640	T641	T642	T643	T644	T645	T646	T647	T648	T649	T650	T651	T652	T653	T654	T655	T656	T657	T658	T659	T660	T661	T662	T663	T664	T665	T666	T667	T668	T669	T670	T671	T672	T673	T674	T675	T676	T677	T678	T679	T680	T681	T682	T683	T684	T685	T686	T687	T688	T689	T690	T691	T692	T693	T694	T695	T696	T697	T698	T699	T700	T701	T702	T703	T704	T705	T706	T707	T708	T709	T710	T711	T712	T713	T714	T715	T716	T717	T718	T719	T720	T721	T722	T723	T724	T725	T726	T727	T728	T729	T730	T731	T732	T733	T734	T735	T736	T737	T738	T739	T740	T741	T742	T743	T744	T745	T746	T747	T748	T749	T750	T751	T752	T753	T754	T755	T756	T757	T758	T759	T760	T761	T762	T763	T764	T765	T766	T767	T768	T769	T770	T771	T772	T773	T774	T775	T776	T777	T778	T779	T780	T781	T782	T783	T784	T785	T786	T787	T788	T789	T790	T791	T792	T793	T794	T795	T796	T797	T798	T799	T800	T801	T802	T803	T804	T805	T806	T807	T808	T809	T810	T811	T812	T813	T814	T815	T816	T817	T818	T819	T820	T821	T822	T823	T824	T825	T826	T827	T828	T829	T830	T831	T832	T833	T834	T835	T836	T837	T838	T839	T840	T841	T842	T843	T844	T845	T846	T847	T848	T849	T850	T851	T852	T853	T854	T855	T856	T857	T858	T859	T860	T861	T862	T863	T864	T865	T866	T867	T868	T869	T870	T871	T872	T873	T874	T875	T876	T877	T878	T879	T880	T881	T882	T883	T884	T885	T886	T887	T888	T889	T890	T891	T892	T893	T894	T895	T896	T897	T898	T899	T900	T901	T902	T903	T904	T905	T906	T907	T908	T909	T910	T911	T912	T913	T914	T915	T916	T917	T918	T919	T920	T921	T922	T923	T924	T925	T926	T927	T928	T929	T930	T931	T932	T933	T934	T935	T936	T937	T938	T939	T940	T941	T942	T943	T944	T945	T946	T947	T948	T949	T950	T951	T952	T953	T954	T955	T956	T957	T958	T959	T960	T961	T962	T963	T964	T965	T966	T967	T968	T969	T970	T971	T972	T973	T974	T975	T976	T977	T978	T979	T980	T981	T982	T983	T984	T985	T986	T987	T988	T989	T990	T991	T992	T993	T994	T995	T996	T997	T998	T999	T1000	T1001	T1002	T1003	T1004	T1005	T1006	T1007	T1008	T1009	T1010	T1011	T1012	T1013	T1014	T1015	T1016	T1017	T1018	T1019	T1020	T1021	T1022	T1023	T1024	T1025	T1026	T1027	T1028	T1029	T1030	T1031	T1032	T1033	T1034	T1035	T1036	T1037	T1038	T1039	T1040	T1041	T1042	T1043	T1044	T1045	T1046	T1047	T1048	T1049	T1050	T1051	T1052	T1053	T1054	T1055	T1056	T1057	T1058	T1059	T1060	T1061	T1062	T1063	T1064	T1065	T1066	T1067	T1068	T1069	T1070	T1071	T1072	T1073	T1074	T1075	T1076	T1077	T1078	T1079	T1080	T1081	T1082	T1083	T1084	T1085	T1086	T1087	T1088	T1089	T1090	T1091	T1092	T1093	T1094	T1095	T1096	T1097	T1098	T1099	T1100	T1101	T1102	T1103	T1104	T1105	T1106	T1107	T1108	T1109	T1110	T1111	T1112	T1113	T1114	T1115	T1116	T1117	T1118	T1119	T1120	T1121	T1122	T1123	T1124	T1125	T1126	T1127	T1128	T1129	T1130	T1131	T1132	T1133	T1134	T1135	T1136	T1137	T1138	T1139	T1140	T1141	T1142	T1143	T1144	T1145	T1146	T1147	T1148	T1149	T1150	T1151	T1152	T1153	T1154	T1155	T1156	T1157	T1158	T1159	T1160	T1161	T1162	T1163	T1164	T1165	T1166	T1167	T1168	T1169	T1170	T1171	T1172	T1173	T1174	T1175	T1176	T1177	T1178	T1179	T1180	T1181	T1182	T1183	T1184	T1185	T1186	T1187	T1188	T1189	T1190	T1191	T1192	T1193	T1194	T1195	T1196	T1197	T1198	T1199	T1200	T1201	T1202	T1203	T1204	T1205	T1206	T1207	T1208	T1209	T1210	T1211	T1212	T1213	T1214	T1215	T1216	T1217	T1218	T1219	T1220	T1221	T1222	T1223	T1224	T1225	T1226	T1227	T1228	T1229	T1230	T1231	T1232	T1233	T1234	T1235	T1236	T1237	T1238	T1239	T1240	T1241	T1242	T1243	T1244	T1245	T1246	T1247	T1248	T1249	T1250	T1251	T1252	T1253	T1254	T1255	T1256	T1257	T1258	T1259	T1260	T1261	T1262	T1263	T1264	T1265	T1266	T1267	T1268	T1269	T1270	T1271	T1272	T1273	T1274	T1275	T1276	T1277	T1278	T1279	T1280	T1281	T1282	T1283	T1284	T1285	T1286	T1287	T1288	T1289	T1290	T1291	T1292	T1293	T1294	T1295	T1296	T1297	T1298	T1299	T1300	T1301	T1302	T1303	T1304	T1305	T1306	T1307	T1308	T1309	T1310	T1311	T1312	T1313	T1314	T1315	T1316	T1317	T1318	T1319	T1320	T1321	T1322	T1323	T1324	T1325	T1326	T1327	T1328	T1329	T1330	T1331	T1332	T1333	T1334	T1335	T1336	T1337	T1338	T1339	T1340	T1341	T1342	T1343	T1344	T1345	T1346	T1347	T1348	T1349	T1350	T1351	T1352	T1353	T1354	T1355	T1356	T1357	T1358	T1359	T1360	T1361	T1362	T1363	T1364	T1365	T1366	T1367	T1368	T1369	T1370	T1371	T1372	T1373	T1374	T1375	T1376	T1377	T1378	T1379	T1380	T1381	T1382	T1383	T1384	T1385	T1386	T1387	T1388	T1389	T1390	T1391	T1392	T1393	T1394	T1395	T1396	T1397	T1398	T1399	T1400	T1401	T1402	T1403	T1404	T1405	T1406	T1407	T1408	T1409	T1410	T1411	T1412

WEIGHTED SUPERMATRIX

Alternative	Objectives										Constraints										Resources										Performance										Sustainability									
	W1	W2	W3	W4	W5	W6	W7	W8	W9	W10	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10
A1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

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